

تفعيل تكنولوجيا التعليم
Activating EdTech

Activating Educational Technology Sprint 4 Report

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Our outputs are archived here <https://zenodo.org/communities/aet/>.

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Summary of Phase I

The first phase of AET focused on introducing a new way of working to Jordan's Ministry of Education. It aimed to introduce Agile Management principles to EdTech decision making. It resulted in 3 Sprints (defined as short periods of intense work), the formation of a dedicated team, and an initial change in working habits. Phase I also delivered a number of micro experiments, the initial pillars of an EdTech Strategy, and a document used to guide the process moving forward.

AET Phase II

Efforts have increased in AET Phase II, and the AET team has adopted an accelerated timeline. The team will be restructured into a Steering Committee, which will be responsible for strategic decisions and reviewing outputs, and a Technical Team, which will produce and implement the EdTech Strategy. The work has also been divided into 5 phases, illustrated below:

Overview of Sprint 4

Sprint 4 ended with an agreement on the priorities for the upcoming Discovery phase, and a clear plan was set for the next two months.

Objectives

No.	Objective	Status
1	Review achievements and lessons learned in Phase I	Achieved
2	Discuss roadmap for Phase II	Achieved
3	Discuss the criteria, tasks and description of the new team	Achieved

4	Identify priority areas to address in the first Discovery phase	Achieved
5	Finalise Phase I Documentation	Partly achieved. To be continued following week
6	Design roadmap for Discovery Phase	Achieved

Outputs

1. Agreement on Phase II plan
2. Priorities and plan for Discovery phase
3. Onboarding new participants

Activities

Day 1

As there had been a long pause between the two phases, and the team has expanded to two other departments (Vocational Education and General Education), the first half of the day was dedicated to bringing everyone back on board. The achievements of Phase I were discussed as were the lessons learned.

A plan was then proposed for Phase II, as was the description of a Technical Team and Steering Committee. Both the plan and description were modified after discussions with the team.

Day 2

The team performed a prioritisation exercise, after nominating 9 different priority areas that we should focus on in AET. The areas included:

- **Systems Approach to Decision Making**
- **Teacher Professional Development**
- Teacher Salary and Recruitment
- Financing
- TVET
- Use of EdTech
- Curriculum Change
- Examinations

- Overcrowdedness and Refugees

These were then narrowed down to the first two (in bold) and the team began formulating questions to be answered in each area.

Day 3

Two squads were formed to begin the Discovery phase for each area, and determined the overarching question(s) for each:

- Systems Approach:
 - “How is data currently used to make decisions in the MoE?”
 - The sub-questions were documented [here](#).
- Teachers:
 - While there was no overarching question agreed upon, several categories were formed with their own set of questions, including M&E, TPD, QA, Incentives, EdTech and TVET.

Day 4

The two teams narrowed down the questions further and agreed on methods to answer them. The teams documented their work (in the Appendix) and begun formulating a plan for the following 8 weeks.

Day 5

The teams began formulating the materials and tools for the Discovery phase, as well as organising the Kanban Board and Google Drive, focusing on onboarding new participants to the team.

Next Steps

1. Receive Ministerial approval for Phase II plan
2. Form Steering Committee and task them to form Technical Team
3. Technical Team to launch Discovery Phase, including performing research activities shown in Appendix 2 and 3.

FAQ

Following are frequently asked questions that were asked during the Sprint, mainly with regards to the new Phase II roadmap.

How does our current and previous work fit into the Strategy?

At the end of each phase (Discovery, Alpha, Beta), the Strategy will be revised to accommodate the new learning. The work conducted during Phase I (the Microexperiments and surveys) will be incorporated into the Strategy at the end of the Discovery phase in October 2019.

The priority areas don't cover all pillars of the strategy, how will we address the rest of the strategy?

There are 3 answers to this

1. **One area, different pillars:** While we have only chosen two priority areas for now, they have implications in several pillars.
2. **Our strategy is delivery:** The strategy is developed and implemented *concurrently*. This means that while the strategy will develop at a rate similar to its *implementation*.
3. **There will be other Discovery phases:** This is an iterative cycle. As we move ahead, we will repeat the Discovery phase with other priority areas, as the original areas move into later stages (i.e. Beta and National Trial).

Appendix 1: Phase II Plan

◆ Sprint

X Progress Report

● Strategy Review

Steering Committee	Technical Team
8 Members	~14 Members (1-3 from each dept)
QRC, Training, Examinations dept., NCCD, Curriculum Department, Vocational Education, Research, Education	
Responsibilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review high-level deliverables Provide strategic direction Approving iterations of the strategy Assigning the Technical Team 	Responsibilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crafting an EdTech strategy Piloting initiatives for scale Collect and analyze data on existing initiatives Develop tools for addressing existing and incoming initiatives Attend a weekly 2-day workshop

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Appendix 2: TPD Plan

الهدف الأساسي:
التحقق من مدى تفعيل التكنولوجيا في عمليات إدارة التنمية المهنية للعاملين في
الوزارة

عينة التطبيق	المصادر	الزمن اللازم للتنفيذ	المعنى بالتنفيذ	متلقي الخدمة	الأدوات	الإجراءات	المكون الفرعي	مجال الاستكشاف
2 مدارس (مدرسة تجريب، مدرسة تطبيق)		أسبوعان	فريق العمل	المعلم، إداري	قائمة رصد و الملاحظة الصفية، مقابلة/ استبانة	جمع الاحتياجات التدريبية	منهجية تحديد الاحتياجات التدريبية للعاملين (معلم، إداري)	الاحتياجات التدريبية للعاملين (معلم، إداري)
٨	قاعدة بيانات للاحتياجات التدريبية في المدرسة والمديرية	٨	٨	٨	قائمة رصد	رصد الاحتياجات التدريبية في المدرسة والمديرية		
	دراسات الاحتياجات			٨	تقرير فني	دراسة		

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	المعدة في الوزارة -2016 2018 والدراسات العالمية				للمطابقة/ مقارنة	الاحتياجات وتصنيفها ومقارنتها بالدراسات السابقة		
					مجموعات تركيز، الملاحظة الصفية/ التقرير للمشرف ومدير المدرسة	تقييم درجة تلبية الاحتياجات التدريبية لحاجات المعلم، إداري.	التنمية المهنية (معلم، إداري)	
				٨	قائمة المراكز المعتمدة	تحديد مراكز التنمية المهنية المعتمدة لدى الوزارة (على مستوى الوزارة ومديريات التعليم)		

						تقييم مدى جاهزية مراكز التنمية المهنية (اللوازم والخدمات اللوجستية والفنية)		
	تقارير التقييمية من المتدربين على البرامج التدريبية				استبانة	مدى مناسبة خدمات التنمية المهنية للمعلم والإداري. (مكان، وقت، مدة التدريب، بدل مشاركة، مواصلات، حضانة، مراسل...الخ)	خدمات التنمية المهنية	
				+ [^] الطلبة	قائمة رصد، مقابلة، استبانة	تحديد التحديات التي تواجه		

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						المستخدمين في نقل أثر التدريب		
	التقارير الفنية من إدارة التدريب ومركز الملكة رانيا				إحصائية من إدارة التدريب ومركز الملكة رانيا	نسبة البرامج التدريبية المنفذة في مجال تكنولوجيا التعليم	مدى توفر برامج التنمية المهنية في تكنولوجيا التعليم	
	منصة تعلم (إدراك)، تقارير تقييمية أو قاعدة بيانات إدارة الإشراف والتدريب، مركز الملكة رانيا				سلام تقدير عددي، ملاحظة صفية	قياس مدى امتلاك مهارات المعلم والإداري في توظيف مهارات تكنولوجيا التعليم		
	تقارير الإشراف				المقابلات (مجموعات	مدى توظيف المعلم أو		

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	التربوي				التركيز) مقابلة المعلم المنسق/ مدير المدرسة، المشرف التربوي	الإداري للمهارات وأدوات التكنولوجيا في التعليم		
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Appendix 3: Systems Approach Plan

كيف يستخدم صانع القرار البيانات في صنع القرار؟

10				9				8	الشهر
4	3	2	1	4	3	2	1	4	الاسبوع
1- التحليل المتمازج (كل الادوات)	تحليل الاستبانة	توزيع الاستبانة و جمع البيانات	تحكيم الاستبانة	1- تحليل مجموعات التركيز	تنفيذ مجموعات التركيز	1- تصميم الاستبانة	تحليل إجابة المقابلة و الوثائق	مقابلة مع رؤساء الأقسام وجمع الوثائق	المهام
2- مراجعة الاستراتيجية				2- إعادة تصميم الاستبانة		2- تحضير مجموعات التركيز			